

Materials and methods

Materials

The polypropylene homopolymer (PP Moplen HF501N) was supplied by LyondellBasell. The polyethylene terephthalate (CumaPET A02-310) was provided by DuFor. The 1-propanol (SigmaAldrich Merck, nr. 402,893, 99.5%) was used as received without further purification.

Carbon tape and aluminium stubs were supplied by JEOL. Au-coated nucleopore filters were from TJ Environmental.

Milling and fractionation

The production of MNPs was performed largely according to the procedure described in 1. The following text and figure are excerpted from this article:

“In order to produce MNP test materials in the desired fractions of < 1 , 1–5, 5–10, 10–30, 90–180 and 180–300 μm , a four-step process was devised. This is illustrated in Figure 1. First, the PP/Talc pellets were reduced in size to below 500 μm in a centrifugal mill (1). Then the powder was further ground in a ball mill (2). The resulting dispersions were then fractionated using sedimentation (3) followed by sieving (4). The final fractions were concentrated to the required 20 mg/ml using ultracentrifugation.”

Figure 1: Procedural scheme for Milling and Fractionation of MNP Test Material. Steps: 1. Centrifugal Milling, 2. Ball Milling, 3. Sedimentation, 4. Sieving

During the production of the particles described in this report, we deviated from the Momentum 1.0 production protocol on a couple of points. First of all, step 1 was either performed using a Retsch ZM100 centrifugal mill (as described), or a Pulverisette 0 Vibratory Micro Mill from Fritsch, depending on availability of equipment. Second, in

order to produce weathered samples, a UV ageing step was performed between steps 1 and 2 of the protocol. For these samples, the pre-milling (step 1) was done with the centrifugal mill with a 500 μm ring sieve, to ensure that the particles had a similar size before ageing. Additionally, after the 1000 hours of ageing, the samples were passed through the centrifugal mill again, in order to break up the larger particles, to allow for more effective ball milling. Lastly, the order of steps 3 and 4 was reversed, so that larger fractions could be obtained and sent to partners before performing further, more time intensive fractionation steps.

UV ageing

UV ageing was performed in a Atlas Suntext XXL+, equipped with three air-cooled xenon lamps, for 1000 hours. Every 12 hours, the particles were sprayed with demi water for one minute, to simulate outdoor conditions. The irradiance was set to 60 W m^{-2} (300-400 nm). The test room temperature and a relative humidity were 60 °C and 45%, respectively. The polymer samples were stirred through regularly, to allow for even exposure.

Leachates

Leachates were prepared in a concentration of 0.05 g polymer particles per mL 1-propanol. The size of the particles used was 20-180 μm . The leachates were left to sit at room temperature for 39 days, after which the particles were removed using a syringe membrane filter.

Static Light Scattering (SLS)

Static Light Scattering (SLS) was performed at two locations: in the Netherlands by TNO and in the United Kingdom by Malvern. At TNO Eindhoven, SLS was mainly performed to check the progress of the MNPs production. This was done using a Shimadzu SALD-7500nano. All samples were measured in 1-propanol. To ensure that the particles were well dispersed, a mechanical stirring unit was used. In Table 1 an overview is given from the refractive indices of all samples.

Table 1: Refractive indices used for the calculation of the particle size distribution from SLS, performed in Eindhoven.

Sample	Refractive index
PP Virgin	1.50-0.00i
PP UV aged	1.50-0.05i
PET Virgin	1.65-0.00i
PET UV aged	1.65-0.01i
PA UV aged	1.60-0.02i
PVC UV aged	1.55-0.10i

At Malvern, particle size distributions were analysed using the Mastersizer 3000+. From the stock solutions 2 droplets was taken and suspended in 1 mL of 2-propanol (IPA). The dispersion was transferred into the cuvette which was filled with IPA until an obscuration

of 4-8% was achieved. For each sample six consecutive measurements were performed and a stirrer speed of 1600 rpm was used.

Fourier-Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy

FTIR analyses were performed with a Thermo Scientific Nicolet iN10 FT-IR equipped with an ATR crystal. Spectra were recorded in a range of IR vibrations from 4000 to 700 cm^{-1} . Data was processed using OMNIC Picta software. Atmospheric suppression and automatic baseline correction were applied.

Scanning Electron Microscopy with Energy Dispersive X-ray (SEM-EDX) Spectroscopy

SEM-EDX analyses were performed with a Tescan MAIA III Triglav field emission scanning electron microscope, equipped with Bruker XFlash Quantax 30 mm² silicon drift detectors for energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy. SEM images were recorded in the secondary electron (SE) and backscattered electron (BSE) modes between 5 – 15 kV.

X-ray Fluorescence (XRF)

The composition and contamination of the produced MNPs was determined with XRF spectroscopy using an Epsilon 4 ED XRF spectrometer (DY6022) and Omnia software. For this technique relatively large sample amounts are needed, therefore only measurements were performed on the remaining fractions after course milling during production.